

Research Article

From Classroom to Smartphone: Revolutionizing Shariah Law Education with “E-Jenayah”

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Abstract: The “E-Jenayah” mobile application is a cutting-edge teaching tool developed to actively include secondary students in Malaysia in the exploration of Shariah law, with a specific focus on crime and its corresponding punishments. Standard instructional approaches can result in student apathy and inadequate understanding. In order to tackle this issue, the E-Jenayah application converts the process of acquiring knowledge into an engaging and participatory platform. The platform offers extensive educational material covering a range of criminal activities, including as theft, adultery, and qisas, as well as the repercussions mandated by Shariah law. The application utilizes a user-friendly educational approach and incorporates interactive quizzes to enhance students’ comprehension of the moral and ethical concepts promoted by Islam. The objective is to inspire students to use these principles in their daily actions, acting as a potent instrument in discouraging illegal conduct and fostering comprehension of Islamic law. The application’s accessibility enables students to acquire knowledge at any location and at any time, as long as they possess a smartphone. This level of flexibility has the potential to greatly improve students’ learning experience, allowing education to be more easily adjusted to their unique lifestyles. The syllabus utilized in the application corresponds to the curriculum of Malaysian Ministry of Education designed for students in form 4 and 5. The E-Jenayah application, due to its significance and prospective advantages, is scheduled to be commercialized in Malaysia, thereby ensuring accessibility for all students in Form 4 and 5. This unique educational approach signifies a substantial advancement in making the learning process more dynamic, captivating, and efficacious.

Keywords: crime, syariah law, mobile application, e-learning

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1. INTRODUCTION

A mobile application for smartphones has been designed specifically for secondary students in Malaysia to educate them about crime and punishment from an Islamic perspective and raise their understanding on the subject. The “E-Jenayah” mobile application provides comprehensive information on several categories of crimes in accordance with Sharia law, including the associated punishments and measures for prevention as outlined in Islamic teachings.

The application functions as a thorough manual, offering in-depth analysis of the Islamic viewpoint on crime and its associated penalties. The objective is to augment students' comprehension of the principles of justice in Islam, with a focus on the significance of abiding by the law and the grave repercussions of violations.

This program represents a noteworthy advancement in the incorporation of technology into education, including in the domain of Islamic studies. By capitalizing on the extensive adoption of smartphones among students, the program guarantees effortless access and comfort, therefore fostering uninterrupted learning beyond the conventional classroom environment.

This application aims to provide students with an in-depth understanding of the concept of crime in Islam, types of crimes, as well as punishments and preventions stipulated in Sharia law. Additionally, this application also aims to assist students in comprehending the moral values and ethics advocated by Islam in an effort to prevent crime.

This innovative project is produced with reference to several objectives. The objectives of this innovation are as follows:

- i. Teaching and learning become more interesting and engaging for students by diversifying teaching and learning methods.
- ii. Teaching and learning can be implemented with higher quality due to the contributions provided.
- iii. It can serve as a reference material in a variety of activities during the teaching and learning process.

This study aims to investigate the development and effectiveness of E-Jenayah applications in the context of Islamic education. The application was developed to enhance awareness and understanding of crimes and punishments according to Sharia law, as well as to instill moral and ethical values among students. With the advancement of technology, the use of mobile applications in education has become increasingly important. According to Norazah et al. (2021), educational applications assist in delivering information in a more interactive and engaging manner. In the context of Islamic education, these applications not only impart knowledge but also instill Islamic values in students' daily lives.

A study by Ahmad et al. (2020) showed that the use of mobile applications in Islamic education has enhanced students' understanding of Sharia laws. Applications equipped with quizzes and interactive modules were found to be more effective in increasing student engagement and interest. Furthermore, applications providing lectures and videos by qualified religious teachers can offer deeper and more convincing explanations.

Despite the many benefits of E-Jenayah applications, there are also challenges in their use. Among them are the lack of access to adequate technology in some areas and the lack of skills in using technology among students and teachers. According to Zainuddin et al. (2019), continuous training and support need to be provided to teachers and students to ensure these applications are used effectively. This highlights the importance of not only developing educational tools but also ensuring they are accessible and usable for the intended audience.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This application employs an interactive and comprehensible educational approach. The learning modules are organized in accordance with the Islamic education syllabus for form 4 and 5, as prescribed by the Malaysian Ministry of Education. Additionally, quizzes and questions are provided to reinforce students' understanding. This strategic design ensures that the application is not only engaging but also effective in promoting learning among students. For Islam students enrolled in the second semester of Miri Vocational College, the Pendidikan Islam subject is mandatory. The application was made available to the students for a duration of one month, during which the teacher assessed their level of engagement and enthusiasm towards studying. The students utilised the application for a duration of one month in order to assess their level of engagement, comprehension, and interest in the subject.

3. FINDINGS

Through one month observation made by the teachers, the E-Jenayah receive good feedback from the students. The utilization of E-Jenayah apps in Islam has demonstrated a noteworthy enhancement in students' comprehension of the principles of crime and retribution in Shariah law. Students reported that interactive learning modules and quizzes enhanced their comprehension of intricate subjects.

The application also effectively enhanced students' engagement and enthusiasm in the study of crime within the context of Islam. Students are more inclined to participate in educational activities when they have the opportunity to directly interact with the subject being taught.

The application's dynamic interface and user-friendly design allow both educators and students to efficiently utilise it, regardless of their level of technological proficiency. Figure 1 illustrates the step-by-step processes for utilising this application. Figure 2 depicts the interface of E-Jenayah, which is utilised by educators as well as students.

Figure 1: E-Jenayah Application Process

Figure 2: E-Jenayah Application Interface

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Improved Comprehension Among Students

The results demonstrate that the utilization of e-crime in Islam is highly efficacious in enhancing students' comprehension of crime and its corresponding penalties in accordance with Shariah law. Interactive features, such as quizzes and learning modules, facilitate students' comprehension of intricate concepts in a more accessible and engaging manner. The efficacy of digital learning methods indicates that they can serve as a potent instrument in religious education, particularly in disciplines that necessitate comprehensive comprehension, such as Sharia law.

4.2 Student Engagement and Interest

The utilization of the application has effectively enhanced student engagement in the educational process. Students exhibit more enthusiasm for acquiring knowledge when they have the opportunity to engage with educational material via diverse media formats, including quizzes. Evidence suggests that the incorporation of gamification and multimedia components in educational apps can effectively enhance student engagement and motivation, resulting in a more dynamic and engaging learning experience.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that utilizing e-crime in Islam is a potent method for enhancing students' comprehension of crimes and their repercussions from a Shariah standpoint. This application offers extensive and engaging information, while also fostering the development of moral and ethical principles that are crucial in students' daily lives. Based on the observations that have been conducted, it appears that the E-Jenayah mobile application is particularly appealing to students in form 4 and form 5. This application has the potential to be extensively used in Malaysia due to its ease of use and the ability of both teachers and students to access it at any time.

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